

(Z)-9-Hexadecen-1-ol (7): The ester (6; 0.18 g) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (0.06 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) at room temperature for 24 h and processed to yield the product which was purified by distillation (0.14 g), m.p. 128–32°/0.5 mm; pmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.87 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 1.3 (20H, bs, 10 × CH₂), 1.9–2.1 (4H, m, CH₂CH=CH-CH₂), 2.45 (1H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 3.63 (2H, t, CH₂OH) and 5.2–5.4 (2H, m, CH=CH).

(Z)-9-Hexadecen-1-yl acetate (8): Acetic anhydride (2 ml) was added to a solution of the alcohol (7; 0.12-g) in pyridine (2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 1 h and then kept at room temperature for 24 h. On work up, the product was obtained as an oil (0.1 g) which was purified by distillation, b.p. 129–32°/0.15 mm (lit.⁵ 128–32°/0.15 mm) (Found: C, 76.52; H, 12.20. C₁₈H₃₄O₂, calcd. for: C, 76.70; H, 12.05%); ν_{\max} 2940, 2865, 1740, 1450, 1370, 1235, 1040 and 730 cm⁻¹; pmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.92 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 1.32 (20H, bs, 10 × CH₂), 2.0 (7H, m, CH₂CH=CHCH₂ and overlapped s, OCOCH₃), 4.06 (2H, t, CH₂OCOCH₃) and 5.40 (2H, m, CH=CH).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director for permission to publish the work and Dr. S. C. Agarwal, Principal Scientist, for interest in the work. The authors also thank Mr. S. N. Sharma for the technical assistance.

References

1. P. E. A. TEAL, R. R. HELATH, J. H. TUMILSON and J. R. MCLAUGHLIN, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1981, 7, 1011.
2. J. P. FARIN, B. FREROT and J. ISRAT, *C. R. Hebd. Seances Acad. Sci.*, 1981, 292, 101.
3. T. ANDO, K. I. KISHINO, S. TATSUKI and N. TAKAHASHI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 44, 765.
4. P. K. BOSE, Y. SANKARANARAYANAN and S. C. SENGUPTA, "Chemistry of Lac", Indian Lac Research Institute, Ranchi, 1963, p. 94.
5. S. CHATTOPADHYAY, V. R. MAMDAPUR and M. S. CHADHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 236.
6. J. N. CHATTERJEA, S. C. SENGUPTA, R. N. MAJEE and S. N. MUKHERJEE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, 14, 220.
7. J. N. CHATTERJEA, R. N. MAJEE and S. N. MUKHERJEE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 733.
8. G. B. V. SUBRAMANIAM, Y. CHANDER and R. C. SOOD, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 414.
9. B. W. BOUGHTON, R. E. BOWMAN and D. E. AMES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 671.

A Novel Approach to 2, ' -Disubstituted Benzo- and Naphthopyran Derivatives

HAMAD ABDULLH AL SEHAIBANI

College of Technology, Riyadh, Department of Chemistry, P. O. Box 42826, K.S.A., Riyadh 11551

Manuscript received 22 January 1992, revised 30 November 1992, accepted 15 December 1992

A substantial number and variety of natural products having a fused 2,2-dimethylpyran ring are known¹. Ellis² reviewed naturally occurring benzopyrans which are 2,2-dimethyl derivatives. 2-Monomethylbenzopyrans or benzopyrans unsubstituted in the 2-position have not been isolated. Burnett and Thomson³ reported the isolation of 2,2-dimethyl-2H-naphtho[1,2-b]pyran and its derivatives from *Tectona grandis*, *Tabebuia chrysantha* and various *Glialium* species.

Methods for synthesis of chromenes have been reviewed⁴. However, as far as the author is aware, no satisfactory general method for the synthesis of naphthopyrans and its derivatives was known when this work commenced, because existing methods failed to synthesise 2-spiro compounds which have photochromic⁴ or thermochromic⁵ properties. In general these compounds can be prepared by a modified Claisen rearrangement by the reaction of the appropriate aryl propargyl ethers in boiling *N,N*-diethylaniline, the ether being easily prepared from phenol with propargyl chloride by refluxing

with acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and potassium iodide⁶. The yield of the benzo- and naphthopyrans are generally good depending on the substituents. In attempts to prepare spiro compounds via this method, difficulties developed in the preparation of substituted chloride from the corresponding alcohol.

The acid-catalysed reaction of a propargyl alcohol with phenol only, using acid catalyst, has been reported⁷, but the yield is usual by less than 10%. Heller *et al.*⁸ developed a general procedure which comprises heating a naphthol with propargyl alcohol and acidic alumina in boiling toluene or xylene to give pyrans without a side-reaction. Surprisingly, this relatively mild condition brings about a Claisen rearrangement when a traditional reaction such as heating to about 120° in the presence of strong acid or base caused thermal decomposition. But these routes failed for the preparation of spiro compounds or gave a poor yield depending on the nature of the substituents on the phenol or naphthol.

This work presents a preliminary result on the synthesis of photochromic pyrans, which were chosen because of their commercial application.

Results and Discussion

The procedure provides practical route to prepare pyrans and spiropyrans. Nine pyran derivatives were synthesised. The reaction involves a Claisen rearrangement followed by 1,5-hydrogen shift, with an electrocyclic ring closure to complete the process.

Scheme 1

Propargyl acetates were prepared by the reaction of an appropriate ketone with lithium acetylide. Lithium acetylide/ethylenediamine complex was added with stirring to a solution of ketone in a suitable solvent such as tetrahydrofuran or dimethyl sulfoxide.

The product was the corresponding of propargyl alcohol, and the alcohol was conveniently converted to the acetate by the reaction with acetyl chloride in a suitable solvent such as pyridine. When phenol, 1-naphthol and 2-naphthol were treated with the propargyl acetate in boiling chlorobenzene (Scheme 1) the expected pyrans were isolated in good yields. No linear naphtho[2,3-*b*]pyran was separated (which can be prepared by the reaction of ketone with 1-acetyl-2-hydroxynaphthalene⁹). The structures of pyrans were assigned on the bases of nmr spectra and comparison with an authentic samples prepared by other methods⁹⁻¹¹. Preparation of pyrans and spiropyrans failed when toluene or xylene was used instead of dichlorobenzene.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Reichert hot-stage microscope with thermometer. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R 32 spectrometer (90 MHz) downfield from the internal standard tetramethylsilane.

2H-*Benzo-* and 2H-*naphtho*pyrans. General method : The substituted propargyl acetate (0.1 mol) was added gently to phenol, 1-naphthol and 2-naphthol (0.1 mol) in *o*-dichlorobenzene (90 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h, then

cooled and washed with NaOH solution and with water. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a gum which was purified by chromatography on silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) as eluant : 2-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran (3a), colourless needles (70%), m.p. 80° ; δ 7.92–7.12. (12H, aromatic and 4-H), 6.05 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 3-H) and 1.82 (3H, s, methyl) ; 2-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-naphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran (3b), pale yellow oil (58%) ; δ 8.35 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, 10-H), 7.65–6.96 (10H, m, ArH), 6.42 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, 4-H), 5.81 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, 3-H) and 1.80 (3H, s, CH₃) ; 2-cyclopropyl-2-methyl-2H-benzopyran (3c), colourless oil (90%) ; δ 6.55–7.25 (4H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-4), 5.35 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 1.4 (1H, s, CH₃) and 0.2–1.25 (5H, m, cyclopropyl) ; 2-ethyl-2-methyl-2H-benzopyran (3d), colourless liquid (90%) ; δ 6.55–7.20 (4H, m, ArH), 6.25 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-4), 5.5 (1H, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 8.35 (3H, s, CH₃) and 1.0 (t, C₂H₅) ; (2,2'-*spiro*-2-cyclohexyl)-2H-naphtho[1,2-*b*]pyrane (3e), pale yellow needles (65%), m.p. 50–52° ; δ 1.35–8.20 (1H, m, H-10), 7.80–6.95 (5H, m, ArH), 6.40 (1H, *J* 9.5 Hz, H-4), 5.55 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H-3) and 2.35–0.90 (10H, m, cyclohexane) ; (2,2'-*spiro*-2-cyclohexyl)-2H-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran (3f), colourless prisms (80%), m.p. 68–70° ; δ 6.9–8.0 (7H, m, ArH and H-4), 5.7 (1H, d, H-3) and 1.2–2.0 (10H, m, cyclohexane) ; 2,2'-*spiro*-2-adamantane-2H-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran (3g), colourless crystals (68%), m.p. 180° ; δ 7.95–7.20 (6H, m, ArH), 7.05 (1H, d, *J* 11 Hz, 4-H), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 11 Hz, 3-H) and 2.40–1.40 (14H, adamantyl) ; 2,2'-*spiro*-2-adamantane-2H-naphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran (3h), pale yellow crystals m.p. 191° ; δ 8.27 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 10-H), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 5-H), 7.5–7.4 (2H, m, 8- and 9-H), 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 7-H), 7.34 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 6-H), 6.55 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.18 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz, 3-H) and 2.60–1.56 (14 H, adamantyl) ; 2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-2H-naphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran (3i), colourless crystals m.p. 60° ; δ 8.30 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 10-H), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 7-H), 7.50–7.37 (4H, m, ArH), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 5-H), 7.10 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 6-H), 6.68 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 6.55 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 4-H), 5.95 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 3H), 5.37 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 1.86 (3H, s, CH₃).

Acknowledgement

The author acknowledges the technicians of King Saud University, Riyadh, where the nmr spectroscopy was carried out and is especially indebted to Dr. S. S. Al-Showiman, Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, King Saud University, for his great help.

References

1. "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", ed. F. M. DEAN, Butterworths, London, 1963, Chap. 7.16 ; G. CARDILLO, R. CRICCHIO and L. MERHNI, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 4825.
2. "Chromene, Chromanone and Chromones (Chemistry of Heterocyclic compounds)", ed. G. P. ELLIS, Wiley-Interscience, Vol. 31.